

Does innovation of algorithm differ in different regions? —— A case study of natural language processing domain

Xiaoting Li¹, Hanwen Xing², Hong Qiao³, Yuzhuo Wang⁴, Chengzhi Zhang^{5*}

¹lixiaoting@njust.edu.cn, ²xinghw@njust.edu.cn, ³qiaohong@njust.edu.cn

⁴wangyz@njust.edu.cn, ⁵zhangcz@njust.edu.cn

Nanjing University of Science and Technology, 200 Xiaolingwei Street, Nanjing (China)

Introduction

Innovation is a key driver of development and plays a crucial role in the growth of a nation. Algorithms, as the foundation of modern technology, drive technological advancement and are a critical factor in global competition (Zhang et al., 2021). The development of innovative algorithms (we call algorithmic innovation) has become increasingly important in determining a region's competitiveness in the digital age.

The Global Innovation Index (GII) uses the presentation of innovative knowledge as one of the criteria for measuring national innovation capabilities (WIPO, 2022). Based on GII, we try to utilize the proposal of algorithms to distinguish innovation capabilities between regions by a more fine-grained indicator. Taking the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) as a case study, we explore which country and when they proposed the high-impact, original algorithms, because influential algorithms are generally more innovative and reflect a country's ability to innovate. After that, we use the number of proposed algorithms as a metric to evaluate the innovation capability of different regions, and compare the distribution of these algorithms across different regions.

Method

In this paper, we first exact the algorithm and obtain the top 500 high-impact algorithms. Then we annotate the attributes of these algorithms and analyze the differences in the performance of the algorithms proposed by different countries and regions.

High-frequency algorithmic entity extraction

We use a combination of manual and machine-learning methods to extract algorithm entities from articles within the NLP domain. Using the algorithm entities and sentences in ACL papers published from 1979 to 2015 (Wang & Zhang, 2020), we obtain the training corpus and then train the Bert+Bi-LSTM+CRF model to extract

algorithm entities from the ACL papers published

between 2016 and 2020. By merging the algorithms from both periods, we obtain a comprehensive dataset of algorithms mentioned between 1979 and 2020. In this study, widely-mentioned and used algorithms within a particular field are considered to have a significant impact; therefore, we select the top 500 algorithm entities with the highest mention frequency with the number of papers as the count unit.

Attribute annotation of Algorithmic entity

We establish a framework to collect various attributes of each algorithm, such as the country and continent of the institution where the first author is located, from the papers proposing the algorithm. These attributes are annotated by recruiting three undergraduate annotators who search for the first paper proposing each algorithm on Wikipedia, and obtain the full text of the papers from academic datasets. The published time of the papers, the country of the first author's institution and the continent of the first author's country are then recorded and are presented in Table 1 as examples.

Table 1. Examples of algorithm attributes

Algorithm entity	Rank	Time	Country	Continent
Word2Vec	6	2013	America	North America
Logistic Regression	40	1958	UK	Europe
Tree LSTM	100	2015	China	Asia
Iterative Scaling	387	1972	Australia	Oceania
LIMAE	449	2019	Brazil	South America

Note: Rank (sort by algorithmic proposed frequency), Time (the earliest proposed time), Country (the country of the institution where the first author is located), Continent (the continent to which the country belongs).

Results

Distribution of regional differences in the total number of high-impact algorithms

The study counts the number of high-impact algorithms proposed and the number of countries associated with these proposals. As illustrated in Table 2, North America proposes the most high-

* Corresponding author.

impact algorithms, followed by Europe and Asia, while Oceania and South America has the least. Among the top three continents, Europe has the highest diversity in terms of the number of proposals from different countries, while Asia and North America have a significantly lower diversity, with most proposals concentrated in a few countries. This trend is consistent with the distribution of developed countries by continent, suggesting that the number of high-impact algorithms proposed is closely related to a country's level of development. In other words, countries with a higher level of development tend to contribute more to the field of algorithms.

Table 2. The differences in proposing the high-impact algorithms between continents

Continent	# high-impact algorithms proposed	# countries to which the high-impact algorithms belong
Asia	88	8
North America	266	3
Oceania	3	1
South America	1	1
Europe	100	19

It is noteworthy that Asia, which is relatively less developed, has proposed some high-impact algorithms comparable to Europe. This may be closely related to the accelerated pace of development in Asia in recent years. This also reflects that the speed of regional development may also have an impact on algorithmic innovation, so we move on the further analysis from a temporal perspective.

Distribution of regional period differences in algorithmic entities

We count the number of algorithms proposed by different continents each year. As depicted in Figure 1, the number of algorithms proposed per decade generally increases over time, with fluctuations across continents, and North America has been leading the way since 1942. This is mainly attributed to the impact of the third technological revolution, led by the United States, which brings the world into the information age and stimulates progress in algorithm research.

Figure 1. Frequency distribution of algorithmic entities at different periods

During the period of 1993-2002, the number of algorithm proposals in Asia grows rapidly and surpasses Europe for the first time, while the number of algorithm proposals in Europe and North America declines significantly. This is likely due to the rapid economic and industrial development in China following the country's reform and opening up in 1978, which leads to a focus on creating a conducive academic environment and promoting the development of algorithm-related research. Conversely, Europe and North America experience economic recession and deficits during this time, which affects research investment and slowed algorithmic research.

Since 2013, the world has seen steady economic growth, providing a favorable environment for algorithm research, and subsequently, the number of algorithm proposals has increased substantially in most regions.

Through the above analysis, we believe that the pace of regional development also has a positive impact on the capability of algorithm innovation. However, the mechanism of regional development speed and level still remains to be investigated by metering methods.

Conclusion

The study examines the distribution of algorithmic innovation capabilities in different regions from both aggregate and temporal perspectives, based on the differences in the number of proposed high-impact algorithms in the field of NLP. By comparison, we come to the conclusion that the algorithmic innovation capabilities are affected by the level and current rate of development in different regions. The results provide a reference and have practical significance for the development of algorithms and related research in different regions.

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